

Correlation Between Institutional Service Quality and Student Satisfaction in Private Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

The study seeks to determine the correlation between service quality and student satisfaction of the select institution. It employed a descriptive-correlation research design to determine the relationship between the two variables, utilizing a SERVQUAL instrument assessing the five service quality dimensions of reliability, empathy, assurance, tangibility, and responsiveness, and the institution-owned Satisfaction Assessment Survey (SAS) to measure satisfaction in terms of people, process, and practice, further grounded by its rooting to Expectation Disconfirmation Theory (EDT). Data were gathered from second to fourth year students across all programs of the institution's college department during the first semester of the academic year 2025-2026. Weighted mean was utilized to determine

the perceived service quality and student satisfaction of the students, while Pearson-r was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the two variables. Results revealed a statistically significant correlation between service quality and satisfaction, as most departments of the institution achieved "Excellent" service quality and "Very Satisfied" satisfaction levels with the exception of departments such as the Clinic, Discipline Office, and Library, indicating potential areas of improvement. Overall, this study concludes that when an institutional office maintains high levels of service quality, student satisfaction greatly increases. To sustain institutional credibility, offices can implement continuous staff competency, streamlined service pathways, personalized student care and improved feedback mechanisms through the established Modular Intervention Toolkit.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Student Satisfaction, Institutional Services, Higher Education*

INTRODUCTION

Institutional evaluation is crucial for determining and upholding quality standards of its product and services. In the context of a private higher education institution, satisfaction of its stakeholders is crucial in gaining loyalty and its market share against other educational institutions (Chandra et al., 2018). Student satisfaction measures the expectations and perceptions students have relating to a service provided by the faculty and the institution (Twun & Peparah, 2020). However, there are few studies that cover institutional service satisfaction in private higher education in the Philippines, as previous related studies cover state and public universities (Arangote, 2018).

Existing research in the country measures satisfaction through general surveys that fail to identify targeted, service specific strengths, and weaknesses. Moreover, there is a lack of study in the country that

focuses on the correlation of the perceived service quality of these services and the satisfaction of the student stakeholders. This study addresses these gaps by focusing on the institutional services provided by the select institution, with the implementation of a dual SERVQUAL and Satisfaction Assessment Survey approach that correlates perceived service quality and satisfaction. This approach of the study does not only enable the determination of the perceived service quality and student perception for each selected institutional service and their correlation, but also establishes actionable and targeted intervention programs for each institutional office weighted by the correlation of the two instruments. The research seeks to correlate the satisfaction levels of students and service quality provided by the selected institution's services. It aims to properly assess the service quality of these departments as well as determining the perception of the stakeholders towards it, integrating a descriptive-correlational approach. With the implementation of aforementioned survey instruments, the study will bring about an in-depth understanding of service perception from the perspective of the main stakeholders of the institution.

According to Pizarro (2019), customer satisfaction surveys are done by institution administrators to identify areas and measure the levels of satisfaction and dissatisfaction based on the results of school-based experiences of students. This study assesses students' satisfaction levels at a private higher education institution's service through the usage of standardized Likert scale-based evaluations. The study covers the multiple service departments of the select institution: Accounting Office, Admissions Office, Clinic, Discipline Office, Faculty Office, Guidance Office, Library, Office of the Student Affairs and Services, and the Registrar's Office, to provide data-driven evaluation and recommendation for overall institutional improvement.

According to Bucad and Perez (2021), there is an increased recognition of emphasizing the importance of meeting the expectations of the students beyond their academic interests. This recognition encompasses the aforementioned offices in the select institution. Kanwar and Sanjeeva (2022) recognized that students are the key stakeholders of any educational institution. Consequently, this important status within the institution shows a necessity for the administrators to uphold excellence across their services. The institutional services that are present in the study play a crucial role in the forming of holistic student development and success via its key role in support structure. It is essential to acknowledge that the institutional services and their responsibilities are varied per school.

There had been no fixed established criteria by the Commission of Higher Education in determining an institutional service's responsibilities. This distinction was established before any form of evaluation to ensure relevance of the data. The CHED Memorandum Order No.9 Series of 2013 however, defines the Student Affairs and Services of a school as a group of support services established by the administrators to assist students in their college academic career. The study's context, meanwhile, distinguishes the Office of Student Affairs and Services (OSAS) as separate from other offices such as the Admissions Office, having their own responsibility distinct from other services. Despite distinction, they all contribute to the development of students. The expected outcomes of the study views how students of the college perceive the quality of services as well as their satisfaction with it. The research's outcomes will provide beneficial results to students, college administrators, and to future researchers who will plan on exploring the topic in a similar manner.

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design, which is well-suited for correlating and measuring student satisfaction and service quality. This design enabled the collection of measurable data to analyze characteristics, phenomena, and relationships between variables such as the SERVQUAL dimensions and the institution-owned Satisfaction Assessment Survey traits. With a non-experimental approach in which variables are described and their relationships examined without manipulation, the

research is appropriate for studies seeking to understand associations in naturally occurring settings (Apat et al., 2023). When approaching service delivery, this allows a comprehensive evaluation and correlation of service quality and satisfaction throughout the research process.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Saint Francis of Assisi College – Las Piñas Campus, an institution that serves as a representative setting for analyzing student satisfaction and was specifically selected for its conducive data-collection environment. To maintain research integrity and objectivity, researchers must disclose any potential conflicts of interest arising from the data-gathering process, including financial, personal, or professional relationships that may compromise the study's overall process and results. The selected study site allows minimal external disturbances and ensures the confidentiality of all participants, safeguarding their privacy and well-being. Ethical safeguards, including informed consent, participant confidentiality, and response anonymity, will be observed throughout the study to ensure respondent protection. Participants in this study will consist of students enrolled in the second to fourth years at Saint Francis of Assisi College – Las Piñas Campus during the first semester of Academic Year 2025-2026.

Sampling Technique

The researchers utilized a simple random sampling method to select participants from the college student population. At the start of the first semester of Academic Year 2025-2026 in Saint Francis of Assisi College - Las Piñas Campus, the researchers requested the official count of the 2nd to 4th year college students enrolled in the institution from the Registrar's Office. Based on the number given, Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error will be applied to determine the appropriate sample size for the study's survey questionnaire.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

Program	% based on the number of enrolled student	Number of participants	Total population
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	26%	61	148
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	17%	39	94
Bachelor of Arts in Psychology	15%	35	83
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	15%	35	84
Bachelor of Science in Engineering	12%	28	66
Bachelor of Science in Education	11%	25	61
Bachelor of Science in Computer Science	6%	14	32
TOTAL	100%	237	568

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overall Satisfaction Assessment Survey Results

Table 2. Overall Satisfaction results per service department

Service Department	Mean	Interpretation	Level
Accounting Office	3.29	Very Satisfied	Very High
Admissions Office	3.4	Very Satisfied	Very High
Clinic	2.45	Somewhat Satisfied	Moderate
Discipline Office	3.13	Satisfied	High
Faculty Office	3.5	Very Satisfied	Very High
Guidance Office	3.4	Very Satisfied	Very High
Library	2.69	Satisfied	High
Office of Student Affairs and Services	3.55	Very Satisfied	Very High
Registrar's Office	3.4	Very Satisfied	Very High
TOTAL	3.2	Satisfied	High

Table 2 shows the overall satisfaction results of the departments. The Office of Student Affairs and Services was rated “Very Satisfied” which indicates a very high level of satisfaction among students. The high level of satisfaction rating suggests that staff professionalism and empathy went beyond student expectations as part of the overall satisfaction, reflecting positive disconfirmation under the Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory. Supporting this, a study by Dugenio-Nadela et al. (2023) found that both empathy and assurance covers professionalism and competence which are the most important key indicators of student satisfaction. Another study by Mabini et. al (2024) mentioned that when service quality exceeded expectations, especially in terms of empathy and responsiveness, satisfaction increases.

The Clinic received a rating of “Somewhat Satisfied” that indicates a moderate level of satisfaction. The results of the weighted mean indicate that students felt the service only partially met their expectations regarding their interactions as part of the overall perception of service quality. Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory explains that satisfaction depends on how well actual service performance meets expectations. Bucadon et al. (2025) confirm that student satisfaction with institutional services is influenced by expectation alignment and consistency, especially in departments handling health and wellness, where gaps in empathy and responsiveness lead to negative disconfirmation. Lastly, findings from another study support the idea that students' satisfaction with the institution's clinic is influenced by personnel traits such as empathy, compassion, and the Clinic staff's competency (Agreda et al., 2025).

Overall SERVQUAL Assessment Survey Results

Table 3. *Overall Service Quality perception per service department*

Service Department	Mean	Interpretation	Level
Accounting Office	3.34	Excellent	Very High
Admissions Office	3.44	Excellent	Very High
Clinic	2.43	Fair	Moderate
Discipline Office	3.1	Good	High
Faculty Office	3.49	Excellent	Very High
Guidance Office	3.39	Excellent	Very High
Library	2.7	Good	High
Office of Student Affairs and Services	3.54	Excellent	Very High
Registrar's Office	3.42	Excellent	Very High
TOTAL	3.2	Good	High

Table 3 shows the overall results to the service quality perception of each department. The Office of Student Affairs and Services was rated “Excellent” indicating a very high level of service quality in the overall service quality perception. Receiving an “Excellent” rating simply shows that the office went beyond students' expectations. This indicates positive disconfirmation, where actual performance goes beyond what was expected, leading to strong satisfaction, a concept under Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory. Micabalo et al, (2020), stated staff competency and professionalism greatly improve student satisfaction in universities. A similar point with Salandanan et al. (2021), who highlighted the importance of staff commitment and the office’s ability to deliver on its promises are key factors in effective and efficient service.

The Clinic was rated “Fair” indicating a moderate level of service quality in the overall perception of service quality. This means that there is a shared perception of unmet expectations across different aspects in the service quality. This suggests that the Clinic struggles with operational consistency. Students may have perceived the services as sometimes effective and often lacking, including in health-related requests or concerns and in delays. The data reveals a need for clearer protocols and more dependable execution. There is also a need for a stronger presence of qualified staff who can confidently meet expectations to further enhance overall service quality. These results are supported by the study by Agreda et al. (2025), which found that students at Bacolod City College experienced inconsistent fulfillment of health-related concerns, delays in service delivery, and unclear protocols.

Pearson-r Correlation Results

Table 4. *People Pearson-r of Clinic*

People	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.957	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Assurance	0.935	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Reliability	0.949	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.944	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.954	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 4 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the People dimension of the Clinic. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.957$), Assurance ($r = 0.935$), Reliability ($r = 0.949$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.944$), and Empathy ($r = 0.952$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p-values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Tangibility showed the strongest correlation. Results show that student satisfaction in the People dimension is most influenced by the department's physical setup such as cleanliness, organization, staff presentability, and resource visibility and accessibility. It is applied in the Clinic's delivery of services such as supporting student and faculty well-being, providing basic medical care, and keeping student health records (Dajac, 2025). This indicates that the concept of a well-maintained environment and presentable staff of the department helps students feel confident and comfortable in their interactions with office personnel, shaping their personnel related satisfaction. This is supported by Dajac (2025), who emphasized that institutional clinics must ensure proper facilities and equipment to ensure effective service delivery in interactions with service staff.

Empathy meanwhile shows the second strongest correlation among the five SERVQUAL traits, indicating that staff's consideration with student issues, personalized attentiveness, and sensitivity contribute meaningfully to how students perceive the alignment of services with their individual needs. In the context of the Clinic, personalized attentiveness to the needs of a student is emphasized in making students cared for and listened to (Ragma, 2018).

The traits of Reliability and Responsiveness also show notable correlations to the People dimension, suggesting that consistent service delivery and promptness are influential factors in shaping satisfaction with the department's personnel-related aspects. Lastly, the trait least correlating to the People dimension is Assurance. Despite that, the trait still indicates that staff competence, confidentiality, and trustworthiness remain relevant to how students evaluate their personnel experiences with the Clinic. Furthermore, the institution should maintain the school nurse's high motivation to increase effort and enhanced effectiveness in delivering health services (Dela Cruz, 2024).

Table 5. Process Pearson-r of Clinic

Process	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.934	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assurance	0.919	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Reliability	0.920	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.926	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.940	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 5 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the Process dimension of the Clinic. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.934$), Assurance ($r = 0.919$), Reliability ($r = 0.920$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.926$), and Empathy ($r = 0.940$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p-values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Empathy showed the strongest correlation. Results indicate that student satisfaction in the Process dimension of the Clinic is most influenced by the department's personalized attentiveness, consideration, and sensitivity with issues of the students. It is applied in the Clinic's delivering of services such as supporting student and faculty well-being, provide basic medical care, and keeping student health records (Dajac, 2025). This indicates that being considered by the staff through personalized attentiveness, consideration, and fostering good communication with students play an essential role in establishing efficiency and clarity (Ragma, 2018).

Responsiveness shows the second strongest correlation, indicating that promptness and flexibility in staff's handling of student requests contribute to their perceptions of procedural efficiency. Efficiency in Responsiveness of a Clinic is essential as it relates to the required service speed and clarity needed to ensure student/patient satisfaction as supported by a previous study (Agreda et al., 2025).

Reliability and Tangibility meanwhile also show notable correlations, suggesting that consistent service delivery and dependability, and a well-maintained physical environment supports confidence of the students in the Clinic's operational processes. Lastly, Assurance has the lowest correlation among the five traits, but still indicates that staff competence, confidentiality, and trustworthiness remain relevant to how students perceive the procedural aspect of the department.

Table 6. *Practice Pearson-r of Clinic*

Practice	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.930	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assurance	0.924	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Reliability	0.918	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.915	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.929	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 6 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the Practice dimension of the Clinic. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.930$), Assurance ($r = 0.924$), Reliability ($r = 0.918$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.915$), and Empathy ($r = 0.929$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p-values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Tangibility showed the strongest correlation. Results show that student satisfaction in the People dimension is most influenced by the department's physical setup such as cleanliness, organization, staff presentability, and resource visibility and accessibility. It is applied in the Clinic's delivering of services such as supporting student and faculty well-being, providing basic medical care, and keeping student health records (Dajac, 2025). This indicates that the concept of a well-maintained environment and presentable staff of the department helps students feel confident and comfortable in their interactions with office personnel. This is supported by Agreda et al. (2025), who emphasized that the aforementioned traits play an influential role in ensuring student expectations and needs are met, as we as ensuring consistent service quality.

Empathy meanwhile shows the second strongest correlation among the five SERVQUAL traits, indicating that staff's consideration with student issues, personalized attentiveness, and sensitivity contribute meaningfully to how students perceive the alignment of services with their individual needs. The clinic and the nurse's personalized attentiveness to the needs of a student is essential in making students' needs and expectations fulfilled (Ragma, 2018). Furthermore, School nurses maintains and prioritize the health and welfare of students (Dela Cruz, 2024). Assurance and Reliability meanwhile also notably influence the Practice dimension of the clinic, indicating the influence of traits such as competence and functionality help meet the needs and expectations of students, as well as fostering consistent service quality. Lastly, the trait that least correlating to the Practice dimension is Responsiveness. Despite that, the trait still indicates that the department's promptness, willingness to assist, and flexibility in handling student concerns remain relevant to how students evaluate the department's service practices.

Table 7. *People Pearson-r of Office of Student Affairs and Services*

People	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.820	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assurance	0.856	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Reliability	0.833	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.764	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.865	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 7 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the People dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.820$), Assurance ($r = 0.856$), Reliability ($r = 0.833$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.764$), and Empathy ($r = 0.865$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p-values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Empathy showed the strongest correlation. Results indicate that student satisfaction in the People dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services is most influenced by the department's consideration with student issues, personalized attentiveness, and sensitivity, contributing to how students perceive the alignment of service practices with their individual needs. This indicates that the ability of the department to make sure students feel cared for and understood plays a key role in shaping satisfaction with the department's personnel traits. This indicates that the ability of the staff to make sure student feel cared for and understood plays a key role in shaping satisfaction with the department's personnel traits, as supported by Friaes et al. (2023) that shows students who felt listened and supported by authorities of school reported higher levels of trust, shaping satisfaction.

Assurance meanwhile shows the second strongest correlation among the SERVQUAL traits, showing that satisfaction is also influenced by the department staff's competence, ability for confidentiality, and trustworthiness to complete services contribute to how students perceive the personnel aspects of the department. In the study of Albarracin (2024), emphasis on the personnel competency and trustworthiness is seen to have an overall effect on the satisfaction of personnel aspects.

Reliability and Tangibility meanwhile also show notable correlation to the People dimension, suggesting that staff consistency and accuracy in administering services, as well as a department cleanliness, organization, staff presentability, and resource visibility and accessibility are influential factors in shaping department personnel satisfaction. Lastly, Responsiveness despite having the lowest correlation, still

indicates that that department's promptness, willingness to assist, and flexibility in handling student concerns remain relevant to how students evaluate their interactions with office personnel.

Table 8 .Process Pearson-r of Office of Student Affairs and Services

Process	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.766	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assurance	0.760	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Reliability	0.785	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.783	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.790	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 8 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the Process dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.820$), Assurance ($r = 0.856$), Reliability ($r = 0.833$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.764$), and Empathy ($r = 0.865$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p-values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Empathy showed the strongest correlation. Results indicate that student satisfaction in the Process dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services is most influenced by the department's personalized attentiveness, consideration, and sensitivity with issues of the students. This indicates that the ability of the staff to make sure student feel cared for and understood plays a key role in shaping satisfaction with the department's personnel traits, as supported by Friaies et al. (2023) in which the study implies students who felt listened and supported by authorities of school reported clarity with services offered and efficiency.

Reliability meanwhile shows the second strongest correlation among the SERVQUAL traits, suggesting that promptness and accurate administering of services contribute meaningfully to how student evaluates procedural clarity and efficiency. This is supported by a previous study from Isaac (2024) which ties Reliability in timeliness, accuracy, and consistency through their findings of disruptions such as long waiting times which negatively affect procedural efficiency and perception.

Tangibility and Responsiveness also importantly contribute to this dimension, indicating that the department's setup such as cleanliness, organization, staff presentability, and resource visibility and accessibility, as well as its promptness and willingness to assist in handling service requests are relevant to how much the students are satisfied with procedural aspects of the department. Lastly, the trait with the lowest correlation is Assurance. Despite being the lowest, it still indicates that the department staff's competence, service confidentiality, and trustworthiness in accomplishing service tasks are still notable factors in shaping student satisfaction in terms of the department's procedural aspect.

Table 9. Practice Pearson-r of Office of Student Affairs and Services

Practice	R Value	Value	Decision	Remarks
Tangibility	0.785	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Assurance	0.763	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Reliability	0.819	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Responsiveness	0.791	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Empathy	0.776	0.00001	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 9 shows the results which indicate that there is a statistically significant relationship between the perceived service quality and the level of student satisfaction in the Practice dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services. The five SERVQUAL characteristics of Tangibility ($r = 0.820$), Assurance ($r = 0.856$), Reliability ($r = 0.833$), Responsiveness ($r = 0.764$), and Empathy ($r = 0.865$) have all displayed high positive correlations with satisfaction, all at p -values of 0.00001, and therefore are significant at the 0.01 level.

Among the five SERVQUAL dimensions, the trait of Reliability showed the strongest correlation. The results indicate that student satisfaction in the Practice dimension of the Office of Student Affairs and Services is most influenced by the staff dependability, consistency, and accurate administering of services. This shows that the students value the department's ability to deliver services in a reliable and consistent manner, which contributes to their confidence in the structure of the office's service practices. The study of Albarracin et al. (2024) support the idea of personnel capability, task accuracy, and overall knowledge which are under Reliability, are key factors to meeting student expectations and needs within the department.

Responsiveness meanwhile shows the second strongest correlation among the five SERVQUAL traits, indicating department staff's promptness and willingness to assist contribute to how students are satisfied with the service practice aspects of the department. A study affirms that department's prompt attention to student inquiries, and addressing concern is a significant predictor of overall satisfaction in meeting service needs (Albarracin et al., 2024). Empathy and Tangibility meanwhile show notable correlations to this dimension, indicating that personalized attentiveness, consideration, and sensitivity, as well as the department's physical setup such as cleanliness, organization, staff presentability, and resource visibility and accessibility, are important factors in shaping student satisfaction in terms of the department's service practices.

Lastly, the trait of Assurance shows the lowest correlation among the SERVQUAL traits. Despite being the lowest, it still indicates that staff competence, ability for confidentiality, and trustworthiness in handling departmental tasks are notable factors in shaping student satisfaction in terms of department practices.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study indicate that service quality is a statistically significant predictor of student satisfaction with institutional services. It revealed that the five SERVQUAL dimensions were generally rated "Excellent" across most departments, with only select departments falling below the Likert threshold. Office departments that indicated service across SERVQUAL dimensions such as the Faculty, Guidance Office, and Office of Student Affairs and Services. Meanwhile, departments with lower service quality remarks such as the Clinic, Discipline Office, and Library scored lower that highlights clear service gaps that require targeted improvement.

Satisfaction Assessment Survey traits of People, Process, and Practice also received high ratings, with most departments having "Very Satisfied" satisfaction levels. However, there were inconsistencies observed in certain departments such as the Accounting Office, where despite scoring high service quality rating consistently, received a lower satisfaction rating in the Practice dimension. Meanwhile, departments with lower service quality remarks such as the Clinic, Discipline Office, and Library show corresponding

declines in the satisfaction levels of students, which indicates service area improvements in the dimension traits. This confirms the correlation between the perceived service quality of services and consumer satisfaction.

The results when the participants grouped based on their demographic profile reveal varied perceived service quality on departments across program and year levels. Meanwhile, the results of students satisfaction when the participants grouped based on their demographic profile reveal varied satisfaction on departments across program and year levels. This further reinforces the select institution's need for standardized service protocol and continuous quality assurance across all departments to ensure fostering of community loyalty, as well as institution need to identify program-specific expectations to better cater to their academic needs.

The highly positive correlation of the two variables through the utilization of Pearson-r analysis further validates the importance of improvements in service quality that will indicate measurable student satisfaction gains not just in service departments, but to the institution as a whole. Overall, the research highlights the found correlation between the two variables of service quality and student satisfaction, also supporting the importance of implementing intervention programs to address identified service gaps to maintain service standards across all institutional

Recommendations include hiring additional qualified personnel to reduce service delays, improve responsiveness and allow the office to better address students' academic needs and personal concerns, particularly for the clinic, ensure that students know how to process concerns or complaints with clear timelines and empathetic follow-through, implement low-barrier feedback mechanisms that allow students to express concerns and responses to the services, display clear service charters and student care promises in physical and digital spaces, and implement a structured student orientation program that introduces the various campus offices, their functions, and staff members who deliver these services. Additionally, future studies can explore the students' lived experiences, narratives, and perceptions of institutional services. Conduct in-depth interviews with students from different programs and year levels to have a better capture of nuanced perspectives. This will give rich detail on emotional and relational aspects of service quality and student satisfaction.

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